

EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE ON TECHNICAL CHALLENGES WHEN ADOPTING CONTINUOUS PRACTICES

This briefing reports scientific evidence on technical challenges to Continuous Practices adoption, their description, categorization, and detection strategies, with respective insights on effectiveness.

FINDINGS

What are Continuous Practices?

To define Continuous Practices (CP), we briefly describe its components: Continuous Integration (CI), Delivery (CDE) and Deployment (CD). CI is a set of practices to integrate the system at least daily to keep it always in a working state. CDE aims to keep the system always in a releasable state by extending CI with manually-triggered automated deploys and automated acceptance tests. Finally, CD goes a step further, targeting continuously pushing working changes to production without human intervention maximizing automation on the mentioned practices, and extending them with provisioning and monitoring practices. For the details, see the full report.

Fig 1. Continuous Practices

How does the scientific literature refer to technical challenges to CP adoption?

There is a vast terminology referring to these technical challenges (TCs).

Socio-technical research about CP adoption has a broader scope and refers to them more generally as adoption problems or simply challenges since they can be both from a social and technical nature. TCs are generally actionable with automation since they concern code, architecture, pipelines, or infrastructure. Still, many social issues are not actionable using automation.

The research focused on technical aspects (like this one) frames these problems as bad practices, code smells, configuration smells, or smells in other contexts like security, testing, pipelines, etc. Of course, not every smell impacts the Continuous Practices adoption, but specific smells hindering such adoption exist.

What types of TCs have been found?

We found nine TC categories: architecture, code, building, testing, deployment, pipeline, development practices, security, and operations.

Architecture TCs are architecture decisions that hinder CP adoption and implementation, like having many services demanding deployment coordination efforts or communicating without an inter-service message broker. **Code** TCs are code smells that impact practices built into CP, like methods with numerous parameters or large modules that may break the build more frequently. **Building** TCs relate to problems in building automation, e.g., having complex or long-running builds. **Testing** TCs relate to issues in the automated test suite, like flaky tests or tests using production data. **Deployment** TCs are problems in the deployment stage itself, like the deployment of

artifacts generated in a development environment or missing rollback strategies. **Pipeline** TCs refer to issues in the pipeline structure, such as build reports with irrelevant information or operations in the wrong pipeline stage. **Development Practices** TCs are dysfunctional team behaviors, like late merging branches or broken release branches. **Security** TCs are problems that expose the system, infrastructure, or process to potential security vulnerabilities like hardcoded secrets or using HTTP without TLS. Finally, **Operations** TCs are problems related to closing the feedback loop between development and operations, like alert flooding (low signal-to-noise ratio) and poor notification targeting.

What strategies have been used to detect TCs?

We identified 121 TCs in the literature review. From these, 21 have no detection evidence. The remaining TCs, which studies present (various degrees of) detection evidence, have a prevalence of using Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) based detection strategies due to their effectiveness in detecting patterns in source code. Detectors for 49 TCs use ASTs for programming languages such as Java, Python, etc. They mostly account for code and testing TCs (i.e. long parameter list, sensitive equality, etc), but detectors can also be combined with dynamic approaches to detect architectural TCs. We found other 24 TCs with AST detectors based on DSLs, mainly related to IaC contexts (i.e. Dockerfiles, Ansible, Puppet, Chef cookbooks), including building, pipeline, and security.

We also found evidence of the use of several other TC detection techniques. Some include pipeline configuration parsing, version control, dependency, and filesystem scanning targeted at source code repository analysis. Others include parsing pipeline execution logs and target CI pipeline execution information. Combined, these techniques can detect 26 TCs (e.g., late merging, fake success, etc) scattered across building, code, development practices, pipeline, and testing.

We encountered less evidence about using dynamic strategies like machine learning, and code instrumentation to detect TCs. The evidence found points to five architectural TCs, and one operations TC. This doesn't tell us about the prevalence of those approaches in the industry, but it might indicate caution on adoption due to little evidence about detection effectiveness, and for being more expensive and complex to implement and evaluate. Supervised and unsupervised machine learning strategies were used in studies when TC detection complexity was too high: alert flooding detection on run-time system monitoring, and keeping the deployment and orchestration of microservices as low as possible in a migration from a monolithic architecture.

IN SUMMARY, from 121 TCs to CP adoption identified in the scientific literature, we found 100 with some level of evidence on using different detection mechanisms. Six TCs can be detected by employing dynamic analysis approaches such as machine learning, and run-time code instrumentation. 94 detectors use static analysis techniques. 73 use some kind of source code parsing, which suggests practitioners leverage AST and other static analysis techniques wherever possible and carefully evaluate more complex detection strategies like dynamic analysis.

Who is this briefing for?

Software engineering practitioners and consultants who make decisions about adopting Continuous Practices based on scientific evidence.

Where do the findings come from?

This briefing extracted all its findings from the Rapid Review conducted by **anonymized authors** with support and feedback from **anonymized company**.

What does this briefing include?

Evidence on detection techniques of technical challenges to Continuous Practices adoption.

What is not included in this briefing?

An exhaustive list of all technical challenges, their respective definitions, and detection mechanisms. See the full report for details about the technical challenges for Continuous Practices adoption.

For additional information about anonymized organizations:

- <https://anonymized01.url.com>
- <https://anonymized02.url.com>